

THE FORMATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AMONG ADOLESCENTS AND ITS IMPORTANCE

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Annotation: In this article examines the main trends in the development of physical education of secondary school students, reveals the factors of the development of physical education of the younger generation, takes into account the individual and psychological characteristics of students.

Keywords: schoolchildren, physical education, educational work, educational institutions, continuing education.

In modern conditions of market relations, fierce competition, as well as serious consequences of the global financial and economic crisis, the accumulation and reproduction of not only and not so much material goods and services, but also the accumulation of knowledge, experience, skills, health, physical and creative level are put forward as the leading factors of development, primarily economic personal development.

The main goal of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as other countries of the world, is to build a democratic rule of law state with a socially oriented economy and the formation of a civil society where human interests are put above all. This means that the most decisive factor in the prosperity of our country and its advancement is human capital, the growing and coming into life of the young generation of the republic, which has modern knowledge and in-demand professions and is able to take responsibility for the future prosperity of the state. It is human capital that makes it possible to adapt to the conditions of globalization of the modern world, to achieve competitiveness, is an important condition for strengthening the economic power of

the country, improving the welfare of its population. In his speech at the International Conference "Preparation of an educated and intellectually developed generation as the most important condition for sustainable development and modernization of the country", which took place on February 26-27, 2012 in Tashkent, President of the Asian Development Bank Haruhiko Kuroda noted that "the economies of the future are those economies that operate on the edge of knowledge, science and technological innovation. Such economies will become the most competitive and productive. They will be able to go through the development phase of a middle-income country and reach the level of a high-income country, form peaceful and stable societies. These knowledge economies will be based on educational achievements, technological excellence and entrepreneurial energy". Consequently, the human potential of any highly developed country is its main competitive advantage and is largely determined by the level of education, the development of a modern system of continuing education, the level of professional competence of teachers. The development of physical education of the younger generation is an archiactual task of our time. Great attention is paid to this issue in our republic. Thus, speaking at a solemn meeting dedicated to the 18th anniversary of the Basic Law of our state - the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the report "Consistent continuation of the course of modernization of the country is a decisive factor in our development", the first President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov noted that "over 1200 new sports facilities have been erected in the country over the years of independence, of which more than a thousand are in rural areas.

This has allowed today to involve more than 260 thousand children in regular classes in various sports". The education system naturally adapts to the situational and prospective needs of the labor market, focuses on the formation of the ability to work productively and social partnership, where, along with the family, a new person is born, his formation as a person and citizen, ideas of honor and kindness are laid, respect for elders, caring attitude towards the younger, the worldview of a young person is formed, his physical and spiritual perfection, his attitude to life. It is the educational institutions

of the republic that are doing a great job in the field of physical education of students and the development of mass children's sports. Educating schoolchildren of an active life position, morality should become one of the priorities of the use of means, forms and methods of physical culture and sports. From the first days of independence, it was noted: "... we must elevate this work to the rank of state policy, turn it into a truly nationwide movement." During the years of independence in the republic: the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On physical culture and sports" was adopted (the draft of the new version of the Law was adopted in 2010), the Decrees of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov "On the establishment of the Order of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Soglom avlod Uchun" ("For a healthy generation"), "On the establishment of an International non-governmental foundation "Soglom avlod uchun"; large-scale research and experimental-practical work is carried out in accordance with the State Program "Soglom avlod Uchun"; The "Program for the development of physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan" was approved; physical culture and sports associations of children and students were created, sports and regulatory complexes "Barchinoy" and "Alpomysh" were introduced; republican competitions are held among students of secondary schools "Umid Nihollari", students of colleges and lyceums - "Barkamol Avlod" and university students - "Universiade", aimed at further reforming the sphere of physical culture and sports, improving the system of training specialists in this field; sports grounds, facilities and complexes that meet modern requirements and are equipped with the necessary sports equipment continue to be built in every city and village; the motto "No one should stay away from sports life" has been put forward in a timely manner to strengthen the physical health of the younger generation in the republic; forms and methods of annual preventive examinations of secondary school students using screening are being improved-programs, automated systems; medical offices with the necessary staff, medical and special equipment have been created in each educational institution; the health-improving orientation of the educational process in general education institutions of the republic is provided; effective forms, methods and means of regulating educational and physical activities

for students of general education schools are being introduced; complexes of physical culture and recreational activities, sports and mass movement of students are being improved to form a medical and hygienic culture of schoolchildren, to expand the promotion of a healthy lifestyle among students through the mass media and popular science literature; a system is being developed to introduce monitoring of the state and health of schoolchildren. Physical education of students contributes to the development of the following personality qualities: speed, dexterity, strength, ingenuity for mastering the elements of technical motor action. In the process of students' physical sports, it is necessary to achieve conscious discipline, honest fulfillment of rules and duties. Various forms of physical culture and sports include traditional (physical culture lessons, physical fitness work during the day, classes in sections and clubs for sports outside of school hours) and non-traditional (physical culture and sports holidays "Bally yigitlar", "Bally kizlar", "Kuvnok startlar", "Football gunchalari") forms and methods. An essential aspect of physical education of the younger generation is to increase the activity of schoolchildren, the active involvement of students in sports clubs, which have a training, organizational, disciplinary nature and most often they are variously combined with each other. The teaching rules help to reveal to the students what and how to do, they relate to the game actions, strengthen their role, reveal the way of actions. At the same time, the rules organize the cognitive activity of students: to consider something, to think, to compare, to find a way to solve the task during physical sports.

All these measures are aimed at further reforming the sphere of physical culture and sports, improving the system of training specialists in this field. Currently, education in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan is a priority function of the state, whose policy is aimed at forming an active, independent, purposeful and responsible personality capable of successfully fulfilling a variety of life roles in today's complex, contradictory and dynamically changing world. Consequently, the organization of physical education of secondary school students contributes to the formation of independence, self-control, mutual control in the relationship between students, the

ability to navigate in changing circumstances, dexterity, accuracy, strength, speed, accuracy of reaction, to show emotional and volitional effort in achieving the goals actually set. As a result, the ability to control their behavior in different circumstances of life is formed. After all, it is known that the development of the above-mentioned physical qualities of students contributes to the formation of a person with a rich spiritual and moral capital. Thus, along with adults, a growing and physically improved generation of young people who have modern knowledge is able to take responsibility for the prosperity of our republic. That is why all the activities of the Government of the Republic, state, public, non-governmental and other organizations are aimed at the formation of a harmoniously developed, morally rich, physically healthy younger generation.

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